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WIPEDESTRIAN: LOW COST WIFI-BASED TRAFFIC MONITORING SYSTEM for TRACKING and CLASSIFICATION of NON-MOTORIZED TRAFFIC --Manuscript Draft--

Full Title:	WIPEDESTRIAN: LOW COST WIFI-BASED TRAFFIC MONITORING SYSTEM for TRACKING and CLASSIFICATION of NON-MOTORIZED TRAFFIC
Abstract:	<p>Non-motorized travel data collection is an important part of the Intelligent Transportation System (ITS), which can be used for transportation planning, infrastructure design, traffic operation and management, etc. However, these data cannot be collected directly from commonly used detectors such as induction loops, sonar and microwaves. This paper proposes a novel low-cost WiFi-based monitoring system—WiPedestrian, which can track and accurately class pedestrians and bicycles. The developed system includes four modules: Data Collection, Data Processing, Feature Extraction, and Pattern Classification. In the data processing module, the Received Signal Strength Indication (RSSI) filtering algorithm for low-speed pedestrian and bicycle hybrid traffic is proposed, which is effective to suppress the environmental noise caused by surrounding obstacles. And then, the travel time and instantaneous velocity characteristics are extracted by the WiPedestrian. Thirdly, the pattern classification module employs a recurrent neural network (RNN) model with long short time memory (LSTM). This study implemented WiPedestrian with off-the-shelf WiFi devices and conducted field data collection experiments at the campus from South China University of Technology, China. The results showed that the proposed RSSI filtering algorithm achieved better signal filtering effects in both static and dynamic environments. In addition, the classification accuracy of the system for mobile mode (walking and biking) is up to 97.92%. The proposed system is a feasible alternative for the data collection of non-motorized travel modes.</p>
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1 **WIPEDESTRIAN: LOW COST WIFI-BASED TRAFFIC**
2 **MONITORING SYSTEM for TRACKING and CLASSIFICATION**
3 **of NON-MOTORIZED TRAFFIC**

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1 **ABSTRACT**

2
3 Non-motorized travel data collection is an important part of the Intelligent Transportation System
4 (ITS), which can be used for transportation planning, infrastructure design, traffic operation and
5 management, etc. However, these data cannot be collected directly from commonly used detectors
6 such as induction loops, sonar and microwaves. This paper proposes a novel low-cost WiFi-based
7 monitoring system—WiPedestrian, which can track and accurately class pedestrians and bicycles.
8 The developed system includes four modules: Data Collection, Data Processing, Feature
9 Extraction, and Pattern Classification. In the data processing module, the Received Signal Strength
10 Indication (RSSI) filtering algorithm for low-speed pedestrian and bicycle hybrid traffic is
11 proposed, which is effective to suppress the environmental noise caused by surrounding obstacles.
12 And then, the travel time and instantaneous velocity characteristics are extracted by the
13 WiPedestrian. Thirdly, the pattern classification module employs a recurrent neural network (RNN)
14 model with long short time memory (LSTM). This study implemented WiPedestrian with off-the-
15 shelf WiFi devices and conducted field data collection experiments at the campus from South
16 China University of Technology, China. The results showed that the proposed RSSI filtering
17 algorithm achieved better signal filtering effects in both static and dynamic environments. In
18 addition, the classification accuracy of the system for mobile mode (walking and biking) is up to
19 97.92%. The proposed system is a feasible alternative for the data collection of non-motorized
20 travel modes.

21
22 **Keywords:** WiFi signal, RSSI, Non-motorized traffic mode identification, recurrent neural
23 network

1 INTRODUCTION

2
3 In the past few decades, with the applications of Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS),
4 the efficiency and safety of transportation systems have significantly been improved. Recently,
5 more and more scholars and transportation officials have recognized the potential of non-motorized
6 travel modes (walking and biking) to reduce congestion, improve environmental quality and public
7 health, and have started to be dedicated on improving the conditions of walking and biking (1-2).
8 However, it is a great challenge to collect travel data about bicyclists and pedestrians on streets,
9 sidewalks, and shared-use trails. The common traffic sensors, such as loops, sonar, video, and
10 microwaves, are not able to efficiently measure and track pedestrians and bicyclists. The reason is
11 that the texture of pedestrians and bicycles is usually weak, unlike motor vehicles, which are
12 limited by lane rules (3). With the popularity of smartphones and the advancement of mobile phone
13 sensors, some new ideas and methods should be provided to address this issue.
14

15 Due to some advantages about data collection (less infrastructure required, easier data
16 preparation and calibration, continuous tracking, high accuracy, etc.), GPS, GSM, WiFi, Bluetooth
17 and computer vision video detection have been regarded as the most referred data source in the
18 literature of target positioning technologies (4-8). Among them, GPS-based approaches require
19 users to install and run a mobile application to actively transmit GPS records to the center, which
20 is not convenient in the real-world. In some studies, GSM data has been suggested as a effective
21 way to track cellphones based on their cellular signal strength. However, the location estimation
22 is very coarse and only appropriate for O-D surveying. Besides, the detection rate of bluetooth in
23 smartphones is usually between 5% and 12%, because most applications involving bluetooth
24 technology are carried out in the vehicle network (9). A widely adopted technology is computer
25 vision video detection. Unfortunately, the performance is degraded when vision obstructions are
26 present and even more severely in adverse weather conditions. Thus, the monitoring and
27 classification of pedestrian activities based on WiFi has attracted more and more attentions with
28 the high penetration application of smart terminals and WiFi network (10-13). In Mainland of
29 China, for instance, the adoption rate of mobile phones has reached up to 94.5%, and about 85.8%
30 of netizens were connected to Internet service via their advanced mobile devices (14).
31

32 Although some researches have been conducted in this area, most has focused on the
33 applications at the indoor environment or data integration with other detections. In addition, most
34 of the previous work based on WiFi did not consider the fluctuation of RSSI. In fact, at an outdoor
35 environment, the RSSI value greatly fluctuates due to unpredicted factors, such as weather and
36 building obscuration. In terms of the selection of classification models, some models (support
37 vector machine, decision tree, etc.) belong to the shallow classification ones, and the recognition
38 accuracy can be further improved. To overcome these gaps in the traditional literatures, the
39 objectives of this study are listed as follows:
40

- 41 • Develop a low-cost, portable and non-intrusive pedestrian network monitoring system for
42 tracking anonymous MAC address of terminal devices in a mixed pedestrian-and-bicycle
43 network;
- 44 • Propose and verify the RSSI filtering algorithm for low-speed pedestrian and bicycle hybrid
45 traffic, thereby suppressing environmental noises caused by surrounding obstacles; and

- 1 • Design a recurrent neural network (RNN) model with long-short term memory (LSTM) and
2 analyze the classification performance.

3
4 In this study, a WiFi-based system (namely WiPedestrian) was proposed that integrates
5 sensors and signal processing algorithms for monitoring non-motorized traffic networks for
6 pedestrians and bicycle traffic. The test was conducted on the campus of South China University
7 of Technology and the performance of the system was quantified. Notably, the developed system
8 is completely independent of the available infrastructure, and can be easily implemented in
9 practice.

10 11 **RELATED WORKS**

12
13 The development and application of non-motorized travel data collection and monitoring
14 systems has always been a research topic of public transportation. The Federal Highway
15 Administration (FHWA) of USA has recently released an updated version of the Traffic
16 Monitoring Guide (TMG), which includes a new chapter on monitoring non-motorized traffic (15).
17 The traditional data detection is through customized surveys, but it includes involvement of human
18 errors and biased responses, as well as being time-consuming, expensive and not representative.
19 To overcome such limitations, many researchers have tried to extend ITS applications to non-
20 motorized traffic to collect qualified data. For example, Zheng et al. only used GPS data to detect
21 the movement pattern, and 76% of the experimental users' mobile patterns can be correctly
22 predicted (16). Bohte et al. used the average speed and maximum speed as key inputs to identify
23 walking, biking and riding, and then combined GIS to distinguish cars and trains. But the
24 recognition accuracy is only 70% (17). Chen et al. used GPS and GIS information to identify six
25 traffic modes with the accuracy ranging from 60% to 95% (18). Stenneth et al. used GPS data to
26 extract features such as coordinate accuracy, average velocity, and average acceleration combined
27 with GIS information, and using a variety of classification algorithms. The results showed that the
28 average accuracy of the classification effect of random forests is 93.70% (19). Feng et al. studied
29 three approaches: GPS only, accelerometer only and both accelerometer and GPS data, which
30 proved that the combination of accelerometer and GPS data can achieve the best classification
31 performance (20). However, it would make these methods extremely battery draining. In addition,
32 it requires the users to open the GPS module or install a specific application on their devices.

33
34 Recently, many researchers hope to use the portable terminal devices as a platform for
35 travel activities inference with the advancement of sensors on mobile phones. For example, Sohn
36 et al. used only the GSM-based trajectories to identify many activities of walking, driving and
37 staying at the same location with the overall average accuracy of 85% (5). Anderson et al. used
38 the fluctuation of observed signal from GSM cell tower to estimate whether a user is still, walking
39 or driving with an accuracy of approximately 80% (21). However, the GSM-based tracking and
40 classification method can only provide coarse-grained recognition accuracy. What's more, Sun et
41 al. used Bluetooth data to classify three travel modes for car (passenger car, motorcycle and truck),
42 bike and pedestrian (22). Due to the limited application of Bluetooth devices, the number of
43 Bluetooth-based data is very little.

44
45 Nowadays, the WiFi-based methods have been getting more and more focus in the recent
46 literatures. To explore the usage of WiFi, Chon et al. deployed a simple application to 25

1 smartphones for a week to record the time spent on WiFi in daily life and the timestamp of WiFi
2 scans. They found that the average participant turned on WiFi 12.4 ± 5.9 hours per day, connecting
3 access points (APs) with 8.5 ± 6.1 hours. As usually, most of smartphones users turn on their WiFi
4 scanning to automatically search for the public WiFi access points (APs) (6). Abedi et al. studied
5 the antenna characteristic effects of BT-WiFi based on pedestrian and cyclists travel-time
6 estimation (23). Lesanid et al. developed and evaluated the performance of a BT-WiFi sniffer to
7 detect anonymous MAC addresses of devices in pedestrian-bicycle networks. The extrapolated
8 results showed an average estimation error of 17.1% (12). Kalatian et al. proposed a classification
9 model based on decision tree-based deep neural network with multilayer perceptron and three
10 decision tree-based classifiers (decision tree, bagged decision tree and random forest). The results
11 showed that the best prediction accuracy is achieved by Multilayer Perceptron with 86.52% (13).
12 For the classification of non-motorized users, some intelligent methods have been reported in the
13 literature, such as Neural Network (24), SVM (25). Compared with shallow classification models,
14 deep neural networks can use implicit multi-layer complex structures and nonlinear
15 transformations to obtain better classification results. In particular, Xu et al. presented a attention-
16 based LSTM network to achieve accurate transmission mode detection (26).

17
18 Despite the reported studies on WiFi sensor for monitoring pedestrian activity, some gaps
19 remain in the literature. One of them is that pedestrian networks are often mixed with bicycle
20 traffic, and the classification accuracy by using existing shallow models (such as SVM) needs to
21 be improved. Furthermore, most of the literatures does not take the fluctuation of WiFi signal at
22 the complex environment into account.

23 **PROPOSED SYSTEM**

24 **System Overview**

25
26
27
28 WiPedestrian consists of four system components, namely Data Collection, Data
29 Processing, Feature Extraction, and Pattern Classification. The system architecture of
30 WiPedestrian is shown in **Figure 1**. The terminal devices with WiFi (smartphone, ipad, computer,
31 etc.) has a unique hardware code called Media Access Control (MAC) that is used to identify it.
32 According to the IEEE 802.11 series protocol, a wireless mobile terminal that turns on WiFi
33 periodically notifies the network of its existence by transmitting a probe request frame on the basis
34 of active scanning. When the nearby AP receives the probe request frame sent by the wireless
35 mobile terminal, it will send a probe response frame to respond (27).

36
37 The data collection module can capture probe request frames broadcasted by the wireless
38 mobile terminal to record these MAC addresses, as well as the signal strength and the connection
39 time within its coverage area. Capturing the MAC address of a wireless device raises concerns
40 about protecting the privacy of its owners. This problem can be solved by encrypting the detected
41 MAC address before sending it to the server. It is also worth notable that the MAC address is
42 specified by the chip manufacturer of the wireless device and does not include any personal
43 information about the device owner (12). In addition, the data packets are stored in an internal
44 database or transferred to a central database via WiFi or GSM. The key roles of the data processing
45 module are listed about: (i) extracting the A and n in the log loss model from the collected MAC
46 address, RSSI, timestamp, etc.; (ii) denoising the RSSI, and (iii) normalizing the RSSI to make

1 processing faster. The feature extraction module further extracts feature information, such as speed,
 2 average speed, and speed variance by converting the RSSI into a distance. The pattern
 3 classification module consists of two parts: LSTM training and prediction. The former module is
 4 to train a LSTM model based on instantaneous velocity characteristics; and the latter module
 5 classifies the pedestrian pattern into two different types (walking or biking) based on instantaneous
 6 speed characteristics.

7

8
 9 **Figure 1 System architecture of WiPedestrian**

10 **Data Processing**

11
 12
 13 In the traffic environment, the coordinates of low-speed moving pedestrians are dynamic
 14 and unpredictable. In fact, the fluctuation of RSSI value collected by the WiFi sniffer cannot be
 15 directly used without processing and optimization. Nowadays, many researchers have presented
 16 the Kalman filter algorithm to eliminate the additive noise superimposed on the signal, but the
 17 fluctuation of the filtered data will have a greater impact on the result. To eliminate this negative
 18 effect, we propose a Kalman-Median filtering fusion algorithm to reduce additive noise. The
 19 algorithm first smoothes the collected RSSI values based on Kalman filter, saves the posterior
 20 estimation value of each iteration, and then performs Median filtering on the posterior estimation
 21 value. Finally, the developed Kalman-Median algorithm can better overcome the influence of the
 22 error, and obtain a more compromised result in the original normal interval.

23
 24 *Kalman filter*

25
 26 Kalman filtering is an algorithm based on statistical theory, and the state vector might be
 27 reconstructed according to the actual measured value and the prior estimation of the system. After

1 the random noise is eliminated, the optimal estimation of the system state is obtained by using the
 2 idea and the recursive model of the correction model (28).

3
 4 a) Calculate the priori estimate of RSSI at the moment $RSSI(t|t-1)$

$$5 \quad 6 \quad 7 \quad 8 \quad 9 \quad 10 \quad 11 \quad 12 \quad 13 \quad 14 \quad 15 \quad 16 \quad 17 \quad 18 \quad 19 \quad 20 \quad 21 \quad 22 \quad 23 \quad 24 \quad 25 \quad 26 \quad 27 \quad 28 \quad 29 \quad 30 \quad 31 \quad 32 \quad 33 \quad 34 \quad 35 \quad 36 \quad 37 \quad 38 \quad 39 \quad 40 \quad 41 \quad 42$$

$$RSSI(t|t-1) = A \bullet RSSI(t-1|t-1) \quad (1)$$

where, $RSSI(t|t-1)$ is the current time RSSI signal value predicted from the previous time; and A denotes the state transition matrix of the system. Since the RSSI value is small in the difference between two adjacent measurements, A takes 1.2 here.

b) The covariance of the priori estimate

$$P(t|t-1) = P(t-1|t-1) + Q(t) \quad (2)$$

where, $P(t|t-1)$ is the covariance matrix corresponding to $RSSI(t|t-1)$; and $Q(t)$ represents the covariance of the system process noise. According to the empirical knowledge, $Q(t)$ might be set to the value of $1e-6$ (29).

c) Kalman filter gain of the system

$$Kg(t) = \frac{P(t|t-1)}{P(t|t-1) + R(t)} \quad (3)$$

where, $R(t)$ is the covariance of the system measure noise with the threshold value of $1e-1$.

d) The optimal estimation of the current RSSI value $RSSI(t|t)$

$$RSSI(t|t) = RSSI(t|t-1) + Kg(t)(\overline{RSSI}(t) - RSSI(t|t-1)) \quad (4)$$

where, $\overline{RSSI}(t)$ is the measured value of RSSI at current.

e) The covariance of the optimal estimation

$$P(t|t) = (I - Kg(t))P(t|t-1) \quad (5)$$

This step is the key to the Kalman filter, which make it work or not.

Median filter

The moving median filter builds a new sequence by moving a window over the raw data and taking the median of the points captured by the window. Using an odd window size, the filter selects the midpoint as an output from a set of points in the window. The observation window can

1 be centered on the sample point so that the filtered output can track the original sequence more
 2 accurately. This means waiting for the RSSI stream to generate more samples of $\frac{2}{n}$ (30). The
 3 computation of a new point using moving median without centering is given by **Equation 6**:
 4

$$5 \quad RSSI_{med} = \begin{cases} \text{undefined}, & 1 \leq t < n \\ \text{MEDIAN}(RSSI_{t-n}, \dots, RSSI_t), & t \geq n \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

6
 7 where, $RSSI_t$ is the measurement in a time series of RSSI samples $\{RSSI_t | t \in T\}$ at a time instance
 8 t ; The sequence is undefined from start up to the window length n since the number of points are
 9 yet not sufficient to compute an average under the specified window length.
 10

11 **Feature Extraction**

12
 13 For the RSSI data of each MAC address, the noise can be effectively suppressed after the
 14 proposed Kalman-Median filtering process. However, the RSSI value cannot be directly used for
 15 pedestrian non-maneuver mode for fine-grained identification. Therefore, one can extract the
 16 travel time and instantaneous velocity of pedestrians from the data captured by each WiFi sniffer.
 17

18 **Step 1:** For any given WiFi sniffer, all MAC addresses captured in the WiFi sniffer are
 19 identified.
 20

21 **Step 2:** Group the RSSI data. First, we extract its corresponding timestamp from the WiFi
 22 sniffer. And then, for each WiFi sniffer, the RSSI data is clustered according to the MAC address m
 23 to generate a matrix D^m , including k detection times of MAC address, i.e.,
 24 $D^m = \{RSSI_1^m, \dots, RSSI_t^m, \dots, RSSI_k^m\}$. In order to implement the grouping algorithm, first sorted
 25 according to timestamp.
 26

27 **Step 3:** Travel time is computed according to the matrix D^m . Calculate the time interval
 28 corresponding to two MAC addresses, as shown in **Equation 7**:
 29

$$30 \quad T_{t,t-1}^m = T_t^m - T_{t-1}^m \quad (7)$$

31
 32 where, $T_{t,t-1}^m$ is the time interval of the timestamp t and $t-1$ in the MAC address m . If the time
 33 difference between two consecutive detections of a MAC address is bigger than a given threshold
 34 (in our case study, it is defined as 300 seconds), then it is considered a new trip for that MAC.
 35 Next, the last time-seen of a MAC address in that group is updated.
 36

37 **Step 4:** Extract instantaneous velocity from the same trip. The RSSI value can be converted
 38 to the corresponding distance value according to the path loss model. Commonly used path loss
 39 models mainly include free space propagation models, log-distance path loss models etc. (31). In
 40 this study, chose the log-distance path loss model to solve the distance of the unknown node, as
 41 shown in **Equation 8**:
 42

$$43 \quad |RSSI| = n \times 10 \log_{10} d + B \quad (8)$$

where, n represents signal propagation constant or exponent; d is distance from sender; and B denotes the received signal strength from the detected pedestrian within one meter.

After getting the distance interval, divide by the time interval, can get the corresponding instantaneous velocity.

Pattern Classification

LSTM is a neural network based on recurrent neural network (RNN) (32-33). The LSTM network is well suited for classifying, processing, and predicting based on time series data because there may be a lag of unknown duration between important events in a time series. In this study, the RNN model is composed of LSTM modules and an output layer for classification. The input vector for the LSTM module is defined as $u_t = [r_t, z_t]$, where r_t is an RSSI value for the t th packet transmission. The structure of the LSTM is shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2 The structure of the LSTM

At the current time step t , the following equations might describe the internal structure of the LSTM module:

$$\begin{pmatrix} i_t \\ f_t \\ o_t \\ g_t \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma \\ \sigma \\ \sigma \\ \tanh \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} w_{ui}u_t + w_{ci}u_{t-1} + b_i \\ w_{uf}u_t + w_{cf}u_{t-1} + b_f \\ w_{uo}u_t + w_{co}u_{t-1} + b_o \\ w_{ug}u_t + w_{cg}u_{t-1} + b_g \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$c_t = f_t \odot c_{t-1} + i_t \odot g_t \quad (10)$$

$$h_t = o_t \odot \tanh(c_t) \quad (11)$$

where, u_t is the input to the LSTM block. i_t, f_t, o_t, c_t and h_t are the input gate, the forget gate, the output gate, the cell state, and the output of the LSTM block, respectively. w_{ui}, w_{uf}, w_{ug} , and w_{uo} are the weights between the cell state and the input gate, the forget gate, the external output gate,

1 and the output gate, respectively. w_{ci} , w_{cf} , w_{cg} , and w_{co} are the weights between the cell state and
 2 the input gate, the forget gate, the external output gate, and the output gate, respectively. b_i , b_f , b_g ,
 3 and b_o are the additive biases of the input gate, the forget gate, the external output gate, and the
 4 output gate, respectively. The sigmoid function $\sigma(\cdot)$ and the hyperbolic activation function $\tanh(\cdot)$
 5 are used as activation functions. In **Equation 10** and **Equation 11**, the cell state, ct , and the output
 6 of the LSTM block, ht , are calculated using the outputs from the above gates in **Equation 9**, where
 7 \odot denotes an element-wise multiplication.

8
 9 Finally, for the pattern classification decision (walking or biking), put the feature vector h_t
 10 extracted at the last LSTM cell through a single perceptron layer where t is the number of packet
 11 transmissions. The output h_θ of the model is calculated as follows:

$$12 \quad h_\theta = \sigma(Vh_t + b) \quad (12)$$

13
 14 where, V is the weight matrix that transfers the values in the Fully Connected (FC) layer to the
 15 output layer and b is a bias factor. In **Equation 12**, the sigmoid function $\sigma(\cdot)$ is used to transform
 16 the logit of the single neuron in the final stage to calculate the probability for classifying the
 17 walking or biking.

18 19 20 **EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS**

21 22 **Experimental Setup**

23
 24 The case study network in this paper consists of four WiFi sniffers, four Android terminals
 25 (Samsung Galaxy Note 2) and a notebook computer (Lenovo Xiaoxin Air 13). The data used was
 26 collected by the DS-007 WiFi sniffer produced by Chengdu DataSky Company, China, which
 27 proved to be suitable for outdoor environments (34). The authors have taken a actual test to proved
 28 that these detectors are capable of recording signals from WiFi enabled smartphones carried by
 29 most network users (34). According to experimental tests, the effective coverage area of the DS-
 30 007 WiFi sniffer can be approximated as a sphere with a radius of 30 meters. Therefore, this study
 31 assumes that when the direct distance between the mobile phone and the DS-007 WiFi sniffer is
 32 less than 30 meters, the connection details of the mobile phone are recorded by the DS-007 WiFi
 33 sniffer. For the purposes of this study, four DS-007 WiFi sniffers were installed in a specific area
 34 (circle consisting of four streets) of South China University of Technology to collect WiFi
 35 trajectories when participants walked or cycled. At the same time, in order to avoid signal overlap,
 36 select the middle block to install the DS-007 WiFi sniffer. Experimental measurement data for
 37 analytical evaluation was collected on July 10, 2019, from 10 AM to 1 PM. The Wushan Campus,
 38 South China University of Technology, has a large-scale pedestrian network with cyclist traffic
 39 (practically less vehicular traffic flow). Therefore, this is a suitable place to test the proposed
 40 system and method. Depicts the coverage area of the DS-007 WiFi sniffer and the direction in
 41 which the participants move in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3 Experiment area and WiFi sniffer location

Performance of the Noise Reduction

In the experiment, there are three scenarios in which the mobile terminal receives the RSSI signal: (i) The transmission environment can be defined as a non-moving environment. The tester remained at rest for 80 seconds, 10 meters from the WiFi sniffer. (ii) The tester started from 15m away from the WiFi sniffer, walked close, then left the WiFi sniffer and walked 15m away. The tester held the smartphone with the constant speed as much as possible during walking. (iii) The tester starts 30m away from the WiFi sniffer, rides close, and then leaves the WiFi sniffer to ride to 30m away. The tester is required to maintain constant speed as much as possible during biking. The ground truth is generated based on several reference points with survey locations. Use a stopwatch to record the time the tester passed through these reference points, and then interpolate to get the true position of the ground between these reference points. In addition, this study assumes that the pedestrian is moving at a constant speed between the two reference points. In scenarios (i) and (ii), two persons as obstacles randomly move between the tester and the WiFi sniffer. The RSSI filtering uses Kalman filtering and Kalman-Median filtering, respectively. The RSSI data collected in the three scenarios filtering results are shown in Figure 4.

This study has used two MOEs to evaluate the performance of the proposed filter algorithm, Average Error and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). The error of unfiltered data, Kalman filter data and Kalman-Median filtered data in three scenarios are shown in Table 1. As shown in Figure 4 and Table 1, some interesting findings can be reached as follows:

TABLE 1 Comparison error analysis of filter in three scenarios

		Scenarios (i)	Scenarios (ii)	Scenarios (iii)
Unfiltered data	Average Error (m)	1.1458	1.3460	1.8526
	RMSE (m)	0.8015	1.1272	1.4464
Kalman Filter data	Average Error (m)	0.6958	0.9651	1.3116
	RMSE (m)	0.5434	0.7037	1.0737
Kalman-Median Filter data	Average Error (m)	0.4474	0.7110	1.1156
	RMSE (m)	0.3181	0.5640	0.9278

- 1 ● With regardless of the average error or RMSE, the Kalman filter algorithm can yield much
 2 more benefits with a small error than the unfiltered data. Meanwhile, these results also prove
 3 that the previous methods are very effective. However, the error peak still has a hysteresis
 4 effect on the Kalman curve. For example, in **Figure 4(a)**, at 70-80s, the Kalman filter curve
 5 is pulled low by the continuous error trough, falling slowly, concentrated in the later stages of
 6 the error peak. In an actual traffic environment, the possibility of a peak error at the end of the
 7 data cannot be eliminated. Once there is a significant error peak at the end of the data, it will
 8 have a greater impact on the optimization results of the Kalman filter algorithm. Notably, the
 9 proposed Kalman-Median filtering in this study can better overcome the effects of errors.
- 10 ● In a static environment (Scenario 1), the average error of Kalman-Median filtering is 0.45
 11 meters, which is reduced by about 60.95% (1.15m) and 35.70% (0.70m), respectively, as
 12 compared to unfiltered data and Kalman filtering algorithm. In the dynamic environment
 13 (Scenario 2), the average error of Kalman-Median filtering is 0.71 meters, which is reduced
 14 by about 47.18% (1.35m) and 26.33% (0.97m), respectively, as compared to unfiltered data
 15 and Kalman filtering algorithm. Thus, the Kalman-medium value algorithm proposed in this
 16 paper can adapt to environmental changes in both static and dynamic environments, and
 17 achieve better signal filtering effects.
 18

19
20

21
22

23 **Figure 4 Comparisons of filtering performance under three scenarios. (a) scenarios (i); (b)**
 24 **scenarios (ii); (c) scenarios (iii)**

- 1
- 2 ● Comparing the walking environment and the biking environment (Scenario 2 and Scene 3),
- 3 whether using Kalman filtering or Kalman-Median filtering, it is found that the average error
- 4 and RMSE of the biking environment are relatively large. This may be related to the fact that
- 5 people in the biking environment move faster, causing large signal fluctuations. It is notable
- 6 that in the biking environment, the average error of Kalman-Median filtering is 1.12 meters,
- 7 which is reduced by about 39.78% (1.85m) and 14.94% (1.31m), respectively, as compared
- 8 to unfiltered data and Kalman filtering algorithm. The results show that the Kalman-Median
- 9 filtering algorithm can maintain better filtering performance even in biking environment with
- 10 faster moving speed.
- 11

12 Performance of Pattern Classification

13

14 In this study, we recruited four volunteers from the Intelligent Transportation Laboratory

15 of South China University of Technology to conduct a data collection process, with each member

16 performing 20 rounds around the designated cycle. Participants used both walking and biking

17 movement modes, each recording the same amount of data. The data recorded by the motion

18 between each WiFi sniffer is considered to have a trip of the respective mode. Since the data used

19 in the analysis is related to the participants recruited, the ground truth transport method is known.

20 After the RSSI data collected in the experiment is filtered, features such as timestamp,

21 instantaneous speed and other derived features are used to train the classifier to infer the

22 participant's movement pattern. To ensure a fair comparison between the different classes, the data

23 set is balanced according to the number of samples per class (in this case 80 bikes and 80 walks).

24 Of the 160 sample runs, 70% was used to calibrate the model and 30% was used to evaluate the

25 accuracy of the classifier.

26

27 In order to find the best classification model, this study compared Logistic Regression,

28 SVM, MLP and LSTM model to train and classify the collected data. The experiment was

29 performed on a Linux system on a Lenovo G40 computer with the CPU model Intel(R) Core(TM)

30 i5-4258U CPU @ 2.40GHz, Python version 2.7.15, and TensorFlow version 1.12.0. Among them,

31 the LSTM model classifier designed in this study consists of a layer of LSTM and a layer of fully

32 connected layers. The activation function used by the output layer is the Sigmoid function, the loss

33 function is the cross entropy loss function, and the optimizer is the output of ADAM. Use the

34 RELU activation function between the output of the LSTM and the fully connected layer. What's

35 more, the size of the output of the LSTM is 5, and the size of the fully connected layer is 1. When

36 the length of the data in a batch is inconsistent, we fill in the zeros in front of the data. An SVM

37 classifier with a linear core is used, where the parameter C is set to 1. The MLP classifier used is

38 set as follows: Number of Epochs:200, Optimization Method: ADAM, Number of hidden layers:2,

39 Input and hidden layer activation: RELU, All hidden layers: 4, Output layer activation: sigmoid,

40 batch size: 20.

41

42 The confusion matrix of the Logistic Regression, SVM, MLP and LSTM models is shown

43 in **Table 2**. The actual movement patterns are compared to the predictions of different movement

44 patterns. The recall rate represents the correct number of predictions for this pattern divided by the

45 total number of times for that pattern. The accuracy represents the correct number of predictions

46 for each pattern divided by the total number of prediction modes. To further analyze the LSTM

1 model designed in this paper, the accuracy and error of training and verification of LSTM during
 2 training are shown in **Figure 5**. One can summarize some following interesting findings:

- 3
- 4 ● The classification process begins with the training of a Logistic Regression model. Although
 5 the calibration process is simple, the accuracy of Logistic Regression is not satisfactory, only
 6 72.92%, which is the lowest of the four models. Compared with the Logistic Regression model,
 7 the accuracy of the SCM model (79.14%) has been improved, but still less than 80%. Using
 8 the MLP model to predict the mobile mode, comparing the first two modes, the recall rate and
 9 accuracy are improved, but not enough. The total prediction accuracy of the LSTM model is
 10 97.92%, and the recall and precision of the labeled observations are above 80%, which is
 11 higher than the respective values of the first three models. The results show that for the
 12 classification of pedestrian networks, the classification performance of the LSTM model is
 13 optimal among the four models.
 - 14 ● Biking is the mode with the lowest recall rate. The recall rates are 59.33%, 58.33%, 79.17%
 15 and 95.83%, respectively. There are a large number of observed bicycles predicted to be
 16 walking. This error may reflect the fact that in a crowded area/time, such as the peak of noon
 17 school data collection in this study, bicycles and walking may share speed-related features,
 18 which may make it difficult to distinguish different models. In this case, the classification
 19 performance of the LSTM model is more stable among the four models. Of the total of 24
 20 biking observations, 23 observations were correctly predicted, and only one biking
 21 observation was incorrectly predicted to be walking.
 - 22 ● From the perspective of accuracy and error in training and verification, the training process of
 23 LSTM is effective convergence, and there is no under-fitting and over-fitting. Therefore, it
 24 can be considered that the prediction results obtained by using the LSTM model for the
 25 pedestrian non-motorized travel mode (walking or biking) in the experiment are worthy of
 26 convincing.
- 27

28 **TABLE 2 Confusion matrix for Logistic Regression, SVM, MLP and LSTM model**

Model	Actual modes	Predicted modes		Recall	Accuracy
		Walking	Biking		
Logistic Regression	Walking	21	3	87.50%	72.92%
	Biking	10	14	58.33%	
SVM	Walking	24	0	100.00%	79.14%
	Biking	10	14	58.33%	
MLP	Walking	24	0	100.00%	89.58%
	Biking	5	19	79.17%	
LSTM	Walking	24	0	100.00%	97.92%
	Biking	1	23	95.83%	

29

Figure 5 Performance of training and validation data on different epochs. (a) Accuracy; (b) Loss

CONCLUSIONS

The automatic data collection on pedestrian and bicycle in the transportation network is essential for transportation planning, traffic design, traffic operation and management, and non-motorized transport facilities, etc. This paper introduces a novel low-cost traffic monitoring system based on WiFi: WiPedestrian. The system can provide the basic functions of a traffic monitoring system, including data acquisition, data processing, feature extraction, and pattern classification. Moreover, as part of the contribution, the RSSI filtering algorithm and pattern classification method for low-speed pedestrian and bicycle mixed traffic are proposed, and the on-site experiments are conducted to validate them.

This study installed four WiFi detectors at four different locations on a designated loop of the South China University of Technology campus, and four staff members walked and cycled on the loop. Preliminary results showed that the Kalman-medium value algorithm proposed in this paper can adapt to environmental noise in both static and dynamic movements, and yield much more benefits on reduction. In addition, four kinds of the classification methods were conducted for evaluation, including Logistic regression, SVM, MLP and LSTM. The accuracy of pattern classification was 72.92%, 79.14%, 89.58% and 97.92%, respectively.

Different from other related literature, the WiFi data in this study is not coupled with other data sources to detect travellers' movement pattern, which makes our approach more cost-effective and easier to implement in practice. Following this research line, one can collect much more valuable trajectory-like dataset for mining, such as road network assessment, origin-destination estimation, activity pattern identification, traffic safety evaluation, and the fundamental relationship between speed, density, and traffic volumes. In the context of future work, this research can be improved in different aspects. Future research will address the following three issues: (a) validation of the reliability and effectiveness of the WiPedestrian system under various geometric configurations and traffic demand patterns through more extensive field experiments; (b) how to improve the selection algorithms and classification methods; and (c) design of a wide

1 application system on urban road network that covers multiple traffic modes, such as passenger-
2 car, pedestrian, bicycle, ground-level normal bus, metro, light rail, etc.

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Under Review